

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity
in polymer processing technologies
of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

**WP1 – ADVANCED HYBRID PROCESSING
TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE DEMANDS
D1.3 EVALUATED BONDING AND
SELF-HEALING BEHAVIOUR OF
DIFFERENT MATERIAL
COMBINATIONS**

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Executive summary

Global annual consumption of plastics is projected to continue surging. This rapid growth, however, brings significant challenges, including a dramatic increase in plastic waste and CO₂ emissions. One effective way to address these issues is by producing more durable products and adopting processing technologies that generate less waste. The IPPT_TWINN project targets these approaches by enhancing our understanding of processing methods and applying innovative technologies. The primary aim of IPPT_TWINN is to elevate the knowledge of polymer processing at FTPO. This goal is pursued through collaborative scientific efforts with four partners from four EU countries, encompassing a range of advanced processing techniques. Additionally, the project includes a variety of events such as workshops, summer schools, and expert visits to foster knowledge sharing and innovation. The project is structured to ensure progress for not just FTPO, but all four partner institutions. While their expertise overlaps, each partner specializes in specific areas, collectively forming a robust concentration of knowledge in modern polymer processing. Moreover, a key objective of the project is to train researchers, particularly young ones, on how to identify suitable calls, find the right partners, and prepare and manage outstanding project proposals.

The primary goal of work package 1 (WP1), titled "Advanced Hybrid Processing Technologies for Future Demands", is to develop a hybrid technology for creating high-performance multicomponent structures with recyclable thermoplastic matrices. This innovative approach merges the advantages of thermoplastic resin transfer molding (T-RTM) and/or injection molding with additive manufacturing in a single production process. By integrating these techniques, the project aims to boost efficiency and sustainability in manufacturing multipart components. WP1 comprises five tasks:

- T1.1: Study of the interfacial bonding strength
- T1.2: Synthesis of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) using reactive extrusion and compounding
- T1.3: Study of the improvement of interfacial bonding strength between different polymers
- T1.4: Use of CANs in hybrid technologies
- T1.5: Development of demonstrators

The main goal of T1.3 is to assess the adhesive and selfhealing properties of different overmoulded and welded materials to aid in selecting the best performing materials with the highest potential for various forms of additive manufacturing (AM) that will be performed in the following tasks.

The present report presents the joined work of all 5 project partners including FTPO, AITIIP, PCCL, BME, and IWK. The report highlights the results of overmoulding, selfhealing, and welding of previously prepared (T1.2), and further modified materials, as well as the preparation of magnetic nanoparticles and their incorporation into the resin. The best performing materials, namely PP-V4-EX, PP-V4-GB, and ABS-V3 were chosen, and further research work will be pursued based on those compounds.

Introduction

The field of polymer materials has seen significant progress since the discovery of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) in 2011 by Leibler et al.¹ Further advancements in this field are driven by the quest for materials with exceptional properties and versatility that CANs represent. CANs have emerged as a fascinating class of polymers with unique characteristics, such as dynamic, reversible bond exchanges.² This enables CANs to show remarkable structural reconfigurability, improved mechanical properties, and the prospective ability to be welded with non-compatible counterparts of the same chemistry. Furthermore, CANs hold the potential for self-healing, addressing the drawbacks of thermosets and thermoplastics by joining the best of both worlds in one material.^{3–5} What sets CANs apart is their ability to dynamically respond to triggers like heat, catalysts, light, or pH changes that can be employed to aid or trigger the weldability, and self-healing.

Plastics joining technologies enclose a variety of methods used to assemble plastic components, either with other plastics or different materials. These methods can be broadly categorized into three main types: mechanical fastening, adhesive bonding, and welding. Mechanical fastening involves the use of screws, bolts, and rivets, while adhesive bonding uses various adhesives to join parts. Welding techniques, such as vibration welding, laser welding, and ultrasonic welding, create strong bonds by fusing the materials together. Each method has its own advantages and applications, depending on the materials involved and the requirements of the final product. Parts can also be injection overmoulded, which is a versatile technique used to create parts with enhanced functionality and aesthetics by combining two or more materials in a single manufacturing process. This method involves molding a layer of material over an existing component, which can be achieved through either a single-shot or multi-shot injection molding process. Overmoulding is particularly beneficial for adding ergonomic grips, improving product durability, and reducing assembly time by eliminating the need for screws or adhesives.⁶ Furthermore, welding and self-healing technologies are revolutionizing the field of materials science by enhancing the durability and longevity of various materials. Self-healing materials, particularly covalent adaptable networks (CANs), can repair damage caused by wear and tear in the presence of stimuli. This self-healing capability is achieved through dynamic bond exchanges that allow the material to recover its original properties after being damaged. Combining these technologies can lead to the development of advanced materials that not only withstand high-stress environments but also have the ability to self-repair, significantly reducing maintenance costs and extending the lifespan of products.^{5,7}

Materials and methods used

Materials used

From commercially available polymers, the following was used:

- PP Braskem C706-21 NAHP (Braskem),
- Exxelor PO1020 (ExxonMobil),
- Graftabond APP-MAH 00530C (Graft Polymer),
- ABS Trinseo Magnum 3904 (Trinseo), and
- Graftabond ABS-MAH 00320 (Graft Polymer),
- Infugreen 810 and SD47770 epoxy resin system (Sicommin Epoxy Systems).

Considering the chemicals, the following was used:

- iron (II) sulfate (Honeywell),
- iron (III) sulfate (Sigma-Aldrich),
- citric acid (Sigma-Aldrich),
- ammonia (Sigma-Aldrich),
- zinc acetylacetonate hydrate (Sigma-Aldrich),
- triphenyl phosphate (Sigma-Aldrich),
- bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA, Sigma-Aldrich).

Carbon nanotubes (Tuball Matrix 822, OCSiAl Europe) and magnetite powder (Inoxia) were used as functional fillers for the preparation of composites.

Overmoulding

Base plates were moulded on Arburg Allrounder 270 S 400-170 equipped with Tool-Temp MP988 tool tempering device. Prepared base plates were overmoulded on Arburg Allround 470 A, e injection 290 (30 mm screw diameter) with Wittmann Tempopro 2 Plus 90. Processing parameters are presented in Table 1, following by the Table 2, which represents the sample list, and Figure 1 where T shape overmoulded specimen is presented, specifically PP base plate overmoulded with PP-CNT. After overmoulding and prior to testing, the thermomechanical dependence of the weld strength was studied on chosen specimen via annealing at 130 °C for either 1 h or 2h.

Table 1: Injection moulding parameters for base plates and overmoulding

Parameter	ABS based materials	PP based materials
Temperature profile (nozzle to hopper °C)	230, 225, 215, 210	230, 225, 215, 210
Screw angular velocity (min ⁻¹)	60	60
Backpressure (MPa)	10	10
Injection speed (cm ³ /s)	45	45
Switch over point	Approx. @ 98% filled part volume	Approx. @ 98% filled part volume
Packing pressure	5 s of 80 % of injection pressure	5 s of 80 % of injection pressure
Rest cooling time (s)	30	30
Tool Temperature (°C)	70	25

Table 2: List of overmoulded specimen

Sample	Description
ABS-ABS	ABS base plate overmoulded with ABS (ABS Trinseo Magnum 3904)
ABS-ABSV6	ABS overmoulded with ABS-V6 (822_2024_0036 in D1.2)
ABSV6-ABS	ABS-V6 base plate overmoulded with ABS
ABSV6-ABSV6	ABS-V6 base plate overmoulded with ABS-V6
PP-PP	PP base plate overmoulded with PP (PP Braskem C106-21 NAHP)
PPMAH-PPMAH	PP-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH (APP-MAH 00530C)
PPMAH-PPV3	PP-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-V3
PPV3-PPMAH	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH
PPV3-PPV3	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-V3
PP-PPCNT	PP base plate overmoulded with PP-CNT
PPV3-PPCNT	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-CNT
PPV3-PPV3CNT	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-V3-CNT
PPV3-OS	Tear testing specimen injection moulded in One Shot
PP-PP_130°C_1h	PP base plate overmoulded with PP annealed for 1 h at 130°C
PP-PP_130°C_2h	PP base plate overmoulded with PP annealed for 2 h at 130°C
PPMAH-PPMAH_130°C_1h	PP-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH annealed for 1 h at 130°C
PPMAH-PPMAH_130°C_2h	PP-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH annealed for 2 h at 130°C
PPV3-PPV3_130°C_1h	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-V3 annealed for 1 h at 130°C
PPV3-PPV3_130°C_2h	PP-V3 base plate overmoulded with PP-V3 annealed for 2 h at 130°C

Figure 1: PP base plate overmoulded with PPCNT

Further modification of vitrimers

For following planned welding experiments, and in pursuit of the most suitable material for additive manufacturing processes existing materials were further modified. First, polypropylene-based vitrimers were prepared using a second matrix (Exxelor PO1020 – sample name PP-EX). The previously employed matrix is regarded as PP-GB (Graftabond). Since previously prepared ABS vitrimers gave an indication of a very high crosslinking degree, and PP-based vitrimers vice-versa, another catalyst was studied (zinc acetylacetonate - $Zn(acac)_2$) which yielded promising results, especially in combination with Exxelor PO1020. In sample names, V4 stands for the combination of DGEBA as a crosslinker and $Zn(acac)_2$ and 0.5 for molar equiv of DGEBA molecules to MA groups in the material. Furthermore, 2 reference samples based on neat PP and neat ABS with additives were prepared to rule out the possibility of a reaction of crosslinker or catalyst with something else than the maleic anhydride group. ABS and PP Exxelor based vitrimers were prepared with 20 wt. % of magnetite powder (ABS-V4-0.5-M and PP-V4-0.5-EX-M) for material to be responsive to induction, enabling welding via induction.

Preparation stayed the same as previously, reactive extrusion was carried out using the LabTech LTE 20-44 twin-screw extruder. Reactive extrusion was performed at 50 rpm^{-1} to reduce throughput and give the components more time to react. The temperature profile was set to drop from $230 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the die to $205 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the hopper.⁸ A list of the additionally modified materials is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: List of additionally modified materials

Sample	Description
ABS V4	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on ABS-MAH 00320
PP-V4-0.5-GB	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on Graftabond APP-MAH 00530C
PP-EX	Exxelor PO 1020
PP-V3-0.5-EX	DGEBA + TPP; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on Exxelor PO 1020
PP-V4-0.5-EX	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on Exxelor PO 1020
PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on Exxelor PO 1020; with 20 % of Magnetite powder for induction heating responsiveness
ABS-V4-0.5-M	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on ABS-MAH 00320, with 20 % of Magnetite powder for induction heating responsiveness
PP-V4-0.5-EX-C	DGEBA + $Zn(acac)_2$; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 equiv MAH; based on Exxelor PO 1020; with 1 % of Carbon nanotubes for laser absorption

Preparation and introduction of the magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) into the polymeric structure

MNPs were prepared via the following procedure:

3,75 g of iron(II) sulfate heptahydrate and 2,97 g of iron(III) sulfate hydrate were weighed into a 1000 mL beaker. 500 mL of distilled water was added to the beaker and the sulfates were allowed to dissolve. A solution of ammonia in water was prepared - 3 mL of ammonia dissolved in 150 mL of distilled water. A pH meter was placed in a beaker. The ammonia solution was added dropwise to the beaker to raise

the pH to 3. This pH was maintained for 30 minutes. Then 250 mL of pure ammonia was added and stirred for 30 minutes. A magnet was placed at the bottom of the beaker and the particles were allowed to settle. The remaining liquid was poured off, the magnet removed and the nanoparticles rinsed with distilled water. This was repeated 5 times - lowering the pH to 10.

MNPs were functionalized with citric acid using following procedure:

a suspension of iron oxide nanoparticles was added or poured into a flask. 9,5 mL of citric acid at a concentration of 0,08 g/mL was added to the flask and the pH was measured to be approximately 5,5. The flask was cooled after 90 minutes and the pH was adjusted to approximately 10 using ammonia. The synthesis result was poured onto an hourglass and placed in the oven to dry.

To include the MNPs into an epoxy polymeric structure, the Infugreen 810 and SD47770 hardener system from Sicomin was selected. The resin inclusion into the resin was studied by DSC and test-pieces were manufactured to study their properties.

The specific introduction of the MNPs into the polymeric system was done through several iterations to achieve a dispersion with the highest homogeneity possible. Some trials were prepared to understand and comprehend the MNP and how an effective dispersion of them could be established. They were introduced into the epoxy resin first to see how they disperse in it. The dispersion was not that good in the epoxy resin part as they tended to clump up. Then, as the Infugreen resin from Sicomin is a 2-part system and the epoxy resin did not disperse the MNP, trials were prepared dispersing it into the hardener. This worked much better. To ease the dispersion in the hardener, a couple of drops of water needed to be added to create the hardener-MNP mixture (H-MNP). Afterwards, the H-MNP mixture was dried overnight in an oven before the final mixture was developed, adding the epoxy resin part (RH-MNP). Prepared MNP composites are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Prepared MNP composites

Resin + Hardener	MNP	Quantity (%)
Infugreen + SD4770	None	0.0
	Raw MNPs (rMNP)	0.5
		1.5
		3.0
	MNPs with citric acid (MNP-CA)	0.5
		1.5
		3.0

For comparison, test samples with no MNPs were prepared to be able to see the capabilities of the MNPs. They were introduced in a 0.5 %, 1.5 %, and 3 % weight into the resin matrix of Infugreen and SD4770. To understand how the composites cure, DSC curing studies were conducted. The RH-MNP mixture was first used for the conversion studies and that same mixture was then used to create the different test specimens.

Self-healing

The self-healing behaviour of the specimen was evaluated via scratch test. Injection moulded testing rods were scratched with the scalpel and investigated using a Keyence digital optical microscope. For each specimen, 3 parallel scratches were made. The procedure was based on an article and adapted.⁹ They were then placed in an oven at 150 °C for 1 h and 3 h. After each of the designated time frames at temperature, they were investigated using the Keyence VHX 700 microscope again. ABS based

specimens were investigated by employing magnification of 100x while PP based specimens needed to be magnified by 300x. Specimens were before testing relaxed at elevated temperatures to eliminate the factor of internal stresses for 2 h at 150 °C.

Welding

Three methods of welding were investigated for welding of the prepared materials. The main and most versatile method employed was ultrasonic welding. Ultrasonic welding was performed using Herrmann Ultraschall Ultrasonic welding machine HiQ DIALOG. Additionally, a few tests were performed with the laser welding principle and induction welding principle. Laser and induction welding tests were limited to the suitable materials, since for laser welding one of the substrates needs to be laser transparent, and one laser absorbent, while for induction welding both samples need to be responsive to induction heating. For laser welding Laser system Novolas WA AT with air cooled laser module 100 W and 975 nm wavelength was employed and for induction iew GmbH interfaces (PLM 727 and TTH8 G) with in IWK made housing. Chosen specimens were annealed at 160 °C and 180 °C in an oven for 2 h. In Table 5 there are presented welded samples with main welding parameters.

Table 5: Welded samples with main welding parameters

Sample name	Welding technology	Substrate 1	Substrate 2	Parameters
W1_PP	Ultrasonic	PP	PP	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_ABS	Ultrasonic	ABS	ABS	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP/ABS	Ultrasonic	PP	ABS	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-EX	Ultrasonic	PP-EX	PP-EX	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-GB	Ultrasonic	PP-GB	PP-GB	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_ABS-MA	Ultrasonic	ABS-MA	ABS-MA	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-EX/ABS-MA	Ultrasonic	PP-EX	ABS-MA	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-GB/ABS-MA	Ultrasonic	PP-GB	ABS-MA	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-V-GB	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-GB	PP-V4-0.5-GB	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-V-EX	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-EX	PP-V4-0.5-EX	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W1_ABS-V	Ultrasonic	ABS-V4-0.5	ABS-V4-0.5	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-V-GB/ABS-V	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-GB	ABS-V4-0.5	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-V-EX/ABS-V	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-EX	ABS-V4-0.5	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W2_PP-V-EX/ABS-V	Laser	PP-V4-0.5-EX	ABS-V4-0.5	100 W, 400 cycles
W1_PP-V-M/PP-V-M	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude

W1_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M	Ultrasonic	ABS-V4-0.5-M	ABS-V4-0.5-M	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W1_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	ABS-V4-0.5-M	Weld time of 2.5 s, 35 % of the amplitude
W3_PP-V-M/PP-V-M_	Induction	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	Local heating
W3_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M	Induction	ABS-V4-0.5-M	ABS-V4-0.5-M	5 s at 120 °C, 5 °C/min
W3_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M	Induction	PP-V4-0.5-EX-M	ABS-V4-0.5-M	5 s at 120 °C, 5 °C/min
W1_PP-V-EX/PP-V-C	Ultrasonic	PP-V4-0.5-EX	PP-V4-0.5-EX-C	Weld time of 2.5 s, 40 % of the amplitude
W2_PP-V-EX/PP-V-C	Laser	PP-V4-0.5-EX	PP-V4-0.5-EX-C	20W, 200 cycles
W2_ABS-V/ABS-V-M	Laser	ABS-V4-0.5	ABS-V4-0.5-M	60 W, 250 cycles

All the equipment used is presented in the equipment overview, which is Table 6.

Table 6: Equipment overview

Nr.	Equipment	Method	Location/Partner
1	Arburg Allrounder 270 S 400-170 (30 mm screw diameter) with Tool-Temp MP988	See Table 1	BME
2	Arburg Allround 470 A, e injection 290 (30 mm screw diameter) with Wittmann Tempopro 2 Plus 90	See Table 1	BME
3	Universal Testing Machine ZwickRoell Z020 with 20 kN load cell	Test speed was 5 mm/min, grips were adapted to test specimens ¹⁰	BME
4	Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 FTIR	Resolution of 4 cm ⁻¹ and a measuring range from 600 cm ⁻¹ to 4000 cm ⁻¹ , average of 10 scans	FTPO
5	Mettler Toledo DSC 2	0 °C to 200 °C for ABS and -50 °C to 200 °C for PP; 2 cycles of heating and cooling with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min	FTPO
6	Thermogravimetric analyzer Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+	5 min isothermal segment at 25 °C, followed by heating from 25 °C up to 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min. At 600 °C atmosphere was switched to oxygen with a flow of 20 mL/min and the heating continued up to 900 °C.	FTPO
7	Dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) Perkin Elmer DMA 8000	heating rate of 2 °C/min, frequency of 1 Hz, and amplitude of 0.01 mm	FTPO
8	Universal testing machine Shimadzu AG - X Plus	ISO 527-1 (1BA specimen) (tensile) and ISO 178 (flexural)	FTPO
9	LabTech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder	50 rpm ⁻¹ ; 230 °C at the nozzle to 205 °C at the hopper	FTPO
10	Injection moulding machine Krauss Maffei CX 50-180	See Table 1	FTPO
11	Melt flow index (MFI) LIYI MFI LY-RP	230 °C and 2.16 kg weight for PP samples and 5 kg for ABS based samples	FTPO
12	Digital Optical Microscope Keyence VHX 700	Different lighting options with different magnifications	FTPO

13	Herrmann Ultraschall Ultrasonic welding machine HiQ DIALOG	Weld time of 2.5 s, and either 35 or 40 % of the amplitude	IWK
14	Induction Welding was performed on combination of iew Gmbh interfaces (PLM 727 and TTH8 G) with in IWK made housing	5 s at 120 °C, with heating ramp of 5 °C/min	IWK
15	Laser system Novolas WA AT with air cooled laser module 100 W and 975 nm wavelength	20-60 W of power and 200 – 400 cycles in the frame of one line	IWK
16	Universal Testing Machine Shimadzu Autograph 10 kN	2 mm/min until the break	IWK
17	Mettler Toledo DSC 3+	Different heating rates for kinetics study	AITIIP

Experimental results

Overmolding

With overmoulding results, first and foremost we need to take into consideration that initial plan was to overmould ABS based plates with PP based ribs and vice versa. ABS and PP are incompatible by the nature and this did not join or delaminated at the ejection of the part from the tool. With ABS vitrimer overmoulding with PP vitimer, adhesion was observed however, due to the properties of ABS, derived from its amorphous structure ABS and corresponding high internal stresses significantly warped due to the temperature on the PP rib at the overmoulding and warpage caused the rib to delaminate. Figure 2 represents ABS-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH delaminating at ejection on the left and ABS V6 overmoulded with PP V3 on the right where significant warpage of ABS base plate can be seen. Warpage further increased by the further cooling at room temperature, to the point where the rib and base plate started to delaminate due to warpage. Thus further experiments studied the influence of vitrimer chemistry on the tear strength of the base plate and overmoulded based on the same matrix. With these further experiments, we need to take into consideration that tear strength results were more or less dependent on the material mechanical properties due to the overmoulded surface connection not being the weakest point anymore.

Figure 2: ABS-MAH base plate overmoulded with PP-MAH delaminating at ejection on the left and ABS V6 overmoulded with PP V3 on the right where significant warpage of ABS base plate can be seen

Figure 3 represents tear strengths determine for ABS based base plate overmoulded with ABS based ribs in different combinations. Considering standard deviation, no significant differences could be measured and due to the reasons mentioned above are dependent on the basic mechanical properties of the measured materials.

Figure 3: Tear strengths of ABS based overmoulds

In Figure 4 tear strengths of PP based materials overmoulded with PP based ribs are presented. Significantly the highest tear strength was determined at PP overmoulded with PP. However, due to PP overmoulded with PPCNT having a very high standard deviation, it could be in the same range as PP-PP. High standard deviation presumably occurs due to the nature of the weld connecting the two tougher substrates and the inhomogeneity or the aggregation of CNT in the composite.

As reference PPV3 was injection moulded in one shot, and had lower tear strength than PP-PP and in the standard deviation range of PP-PPCNT, but still higher than the rest of the overmoulds. As previously with PP based samples again the tear did not occur at the overmould, but in the rib thus results strongly depend on the basic mechanical properties of used materials.

Figure 4: Tear strength of PP based plated overmoulded with PP based materials

As described in the previous chapter, chosen specimens were annealed at 130 °C either for 1 h or 2 h, and the determined tear strengths are presented in Figure 5. Generally, annealing did not significantly influence the measured tear strength, but decreasing trends are indicated with PP-PP and PPMAH-PPMAH. With PPV3-PPV3 the decrease of tear strength with increasing time of annealing is higher and statistically significant. As previously mentioned, the tear strengths seem to be dependent on the basic mechanical properties of the materials thus tear strengths could be decreasing due to thermal degradation starting to affect the mechanical properties in 1 h and 2 h at 130 °C. Besides the degradation, the highest standard deviation is recorded at the toughest substrates and this could be one of the possible reasons for such phenomena. The deviation increases with a longer annealing time corresponds with this hypothesis, PP might crystallize further and faster at elevated temperatures thus resulting in tougher substrates.

Figure 5: Annealing of PP based overmoulds

Preparation and introduction of the magnetic nanoparticles (MNP) into the polymeric structure

Preparation of MNPs

The preparation and functionalization of MNPs are presented in Figures 6 – 8. In Figure 6 the three main steps of preparation are shown. First is the dissolution of iron sulphates in water, followed by ammonia solution addition with half an hour of pH level maintenance and half an hour of mixing after 250 mL of ammonia addition.

Figure 6: Sulphates in water (A), ammonia addition and pH level maintenance (B), and mixing after addition of 250 mL ammonia

In Figure 7 the deposition of the MNPs on the bottom with the assistance of a magnet is shown, and the final product.

Figure 7: MNP deposition on the magnet (A) and the final MNP product (B)

Figure 8 presents the apparatus for functionalization and functionalization of MNPs in the apparatus.

Figure 8: Apparatus for functionalization (A) and functionalization of MNPs (B)

Introduction of MNPs into the polymeric structure

The conversational studies provided us with an estimation of the curing time of the mixture at the DSC level. It was then seen that the different mixtures had different curing times depending on the quantity of MNPs introduced and their nature, as presented in Figures 9-12.

Kinetic Study of RH(Sicomini) + rMNP

Figure 9: DSC thermographs of RH(Sicomin) + 0.5% rMNP

Figure 10: DSC thermographs of RH(Sicomin) + 1.5% rMNP

Figure 11: RH(Sicomin) + 3% rMNP

Figure 12: RH(Sicomin)

The general cure temperature used for the resin is 80 °C. Looking at the curing time at that same temperature the three graphs indicated up here show a reduction of the curing times in all the RH+rMNP mixtures. It is obtained at 0.5 % a 30-minute difference from the virgin resin obtaining a maximum reduction of 1.5 % and coming back to approx. 90 min mark at 3 %.

The test pieces produced were tensile bars (Figure 13), and 1- and 2-diameter circular ones.

Figure 13: RH(Sicomin) + rMNP test-pieces

Kinetic Study of RH(Sicomin) + MNP-CA

As mentioned in the previous RH(Sicomin)+ rMNP, the resin is cured at 80 °C. The 0.5 % does not show any difference with the virgin resin but once the quantity is increased to 1.5 % the time suddenly drops to only 40 min curing time. Again, once it is increased to 3 % the time is increased back again as presented in Figure 14-17.

Figure 14: RH(Sicomin) + 0.5% MNP-CA

Figure 15: RH(Sicomin) + 1.5% MNP-CA

Figure 16: RH(Sicomin) + 3% MNP-CA

Figure 17: RH(Sicomin)

Once again the test-pieces produced were tensile bars and 1- and 2-diameter circular ones presented in Figure 18.

Figure 18: RH(Sicomin) + MNP-CA test-pieces

AITIIP studied the test pieces with SEM but no results were able to be obtained as the resin did not conduct and MNPs were fully covered by it. The surface was then studied for the presence of iron from the nanoparticles with Quantax for SEM. The 3 % MNP samples were used. The quantities obtained were not seen at the surface due to full coverage with resin, as shown in Figure 19.

El	Series	unn. C [wt.%]	norm. C [wt.%]	Atom. C [at.%]	Error (2 Sigma) [wt.%]
C	K-series	70.66	70.66	76.80	15.83
N	K-series	7.76	7.76	7.24	2.90
O	K-series	17.86	17.86	14.58	4.81
Si	K-series	1.74	1.74	0.81	0.20
Cl	K-series	0.85	0.85	0.31	0.11
Fe	K-series	1.13	1.13	0.26	0.15
Total:		100.00	100.00	100.00	

Figure 19: SEM results

Selfhealing

Selfhealing was evaluated by employing a scratch test. ABS seen in the first column of Figure 20 surprisingly reversed the damage the most, followed by the ABS-MAH in the second column. ABS-MAH reversed the most damage after 1 h, however after an additional 2 h the scratch seemed to start widening a bit again, and the material colour changed as well so probably the material is less thermally stable and some thermal degradation might started to take place. ABSV3 seemed to minimally reverse the scratch after 1 h at 150 °C however, no further changes can be noticed after an additional 2 h at 150 °C.

Figure 20: ABS-based specimens in columns 1 – ABS, 2 – ABS-MAH, 3 – ABSV3, and in rows under a) before healing, b) after 1 h in the oven, and under c) after 3h in the oven; magnified by 100x

In Figure 21 neat PP, PPGB, PPV3GB, and PPV4GB are presented before and after “selfhealing” at 150 °C for 1 h and 3 h. As previously highest regression of the scratch is noticed at neat material. With grafted PP (PPGB) the scratch is increasing significantly. With PPV3GB the scratch is also increasing, however less than with grafted material. With PPV4GB the scratch increased the most dramatically, but the increase seems to be more significant after 1 h, and after an additional 2 h minimal decrease is indicated rather than the further widening of the scratch, presumably due to the thermoplastic nature of the matrix which widens with the increase in temperature.

Figure 21: Neat PP specimens in column 1, PP-GB in column 2, PPV3GB in column 3 and PPV4GB in column 4; in rows under a) before healing, b) after 1 h in the oven, and under c) after 3h in the oven; magnified by 300x

With Exxelor PO 1020 based materials no increases in scratches were recorded in Figure 22. The scratch of the reference sample (PPEX – 1 column) is minimally reversing over time. With PPV3EX in the second column, higher regression is indicated after 1 h at 150 °C and no significant change after 2 additional hours. A very similar outcome is recorded with PPV4EX.

Figure 22: PPEX specimens in column 1, PPV3EX in column 2, and PPV4EX in column 3; in rows under a) before healing, b) after 1 h in the oven, and under c) after 3h in the oven; magnified by 300x

Selfhealing yielded surprising results. Neat polymers had the biggest selfhealing effect. With PPGB scratches increased however, with PPV3GB less than at PPGB, while with PPV4GB system, more than at PPGB. PPEX based materials showed similar degrees of scratch regression. Since influence of the internal stressed have been excluded by its relaxation before testing, influences of different materials properties, structure and conformation seem to be affecting scratch regression/progression processes at elevated temperatures. In some cases scratch regression is evident, however highest is recorded for neat ABS and comparing vitrimers to grafted matrixes only PPV3GB seems to show significantly positive influence.

Welding

Welding of materials was performed according to the plan presented in the previous chapter. In Table 8 there are weld strength results presented. With ultrasonic welding of substrates of the same material or matrix, the weld was stronger than the sample in every case. There was no adhesion recorded at ultrasonic welding of neat PP and neat ABS. Both grafted PPs adhered to grafted ABS however with Exxelor significantly higher standard deviation was measured. With PP-V-GB and ABS-V weld strength decreased compared to the adhesion of grafted polymers. On the other hand, with Exxelor based materials it stayed in the range of standard deviation. Magnetite addition to vitrimer indicates an increase however the values are still in the range of standard deviation. Induction welding resulted in weld strength of 0.36 ± 0.06 MPa for W3_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M, while with W3_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M sample

broke instead of weld. Sample W3_PP-V-M/PP-V-M was not measured due to too local heating, that can be seen in Figure 11, as well as other samples welded by induction.

Table 7: Weld Strength results

Sample	Weld Strength (MPa)
W1_PP	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_ABS	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP/ABS	No adhesion
W1_PP-EX	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP-GB	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_ABS-MA	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP-EX/ABS-MA	0.43 ± 0.23
W1_PP-GB/ABS-MA	0.21 ± 0.04
W1_PP-V-GB	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP-V-EX	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_ABS-V	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP-V-GB/ABS-V	0.11 ± 0.01
W1_PP-V-EX/ABS-V	0.48 ± 0.08
W2_PP-V-EX/ABS-V	No adhesion, ABS proved to be laser transparent
W1_PP-V-M/PP-V-M	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M	Sample breaks, not the weld
W1_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M	0.67 ± 0.20
W3_PP-V-M/PP-V-M	Local melting
W3_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M	Sample breaks, not the weld (Figure 25)
W3_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M	0.36 ± 0.06 (Figure 25)
W1_PP-V-EX/PP-V-C	Sample breaks, not the weld
W2_PP-V-EX/PP-V-C	Sample breaks, not the weld at the laser welded line (Figure 24)
W2_ABS-V/ABS-V-M	Sample breaks, not the weld at the laser welded line

Chosen specimens were annealed at 160 °C and 180 °C for 2 h. Since the ultrasonic welding times are short, too short for transesterification to take place up to a significant degree grafted reference specimens and welded vitrimer samples, as well as W1_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M were annealed, to follow the effect of the annealing, which should not affect the combinations of grafted polymers and positively affect the weld strength of the vitrimer combinations. Samples prior to and after annealing for 2 h at 180 °C are presented in Figure 23. With Exxelor PO 1020 based materials nor vitrimers, no references broke at the weld after being annealed at 160 °C for 2 h. After annealing at 180 °C only vitrimers were measured, since Exxelor PO 1020 melted too much. Vitrimer samples did not break at the weld either. With PPGB based specimens, break occurred at the weld. Results are presented in Table 7. With the samples where no standard deviation is recorded, only one sample was measured, due to running out of material to produce the samples. With annealing and an increase in temperature, we are getting increasing weld strengths. The increase is indicated at the combination of grafted polymers however, does seem to be significantly smaller than in the case of the vitrimer combination, thus indicating the presence of covalent adaptable bonding.

Table 8: Weld strength of PPGb based specimens

Sample	Weld strength (MPa)
W1_PP-GB/ABS-MA	0.21 ± 0.04
W1_PP-GB/ABS-MA – 160 °C	0.27
W1_PP-GB/ABS-MA – 180 °C	0.37
W1_PP-V-GB/ABS-V	0.11 ± 0.01
W1_PP-V-GB/ABS-V – 160°C	0.34 ± 0.04
W1_PP-V-GB/ABS-V – 180°C	0.61 ± 0.20

Figure 23: Specimen welded by ultrasonic welding prior to annealing (left) and after 2 h on 180 °C (right)

Figure 24: Laser welded W2_PP-V-EX/PP-V-C

Figure 25: W3_PP-V-M/PP-V-M (left), W3_PP-V-M/ABS-V-M (middle) and W3_ABS-V-M/ABS-V-M (right) welded by induction

Conclusions

Main goal of Task 1.3 of WP1 of IPPT_TWINN was to study improvement of interfacial bonding strength between different polymers. Different materials, including unmodified thermoplastics, thermoplastic composites, CAN, CAN composites were injection overmoulded onto substrates, welded, and evaluated for their selfhealing behaviour. Post processing procedures that indicated the prospect of improving the adhesive behaviour of overmoulds and welds, such as annealing, were studied which provided information on the thermal dependence of the mechanical strength of the weld. Based on the gathered results best performing compounds were selected and will be further developed for the preparation of materials suitable for various forms of additive manufacturing processes.

First, overmoulding properties were evaluated. Overmoulding of a base plate with a rib out of incompatible material, neat, nor grafted did yield in adhesion. The base plate and sample delaminated at part ejection. With overmoulding of the vitrimer base plate and vitrimer rib out of incompatible material, the adhesion was recorded however, due to internal stresses base plate significantly warped and caused delamination after ejection. Overmoulding of base plate with the rib from the material of the same type of matrix material resulted in strong welds that did not break at the weld, but the breakage was somewhere on the rib thus determined results significantly depended on the mechanical properties of welded materials.

Further modification of existing vitrimers with a newly introduced catalyst was performed, as well as the introduction of magnetite powder as a functional filler for the responsiveness of the material to the induction. Magnetic nanoparticles were prepared and introduced to the epoxy system of which kinetics was evaluated.

Selfhealing was studied employing the scratch test. Selfhealing results were surprising since neat polymers indicated significant selfhealing effects. One PP-MAH matrix resulted in a significant increase of scratch and the other one in minimal regression. In dependence of vitrimer and matrix combinations, the results were miscellaneous. Since the influence of the internal stress has been excluded by its relaxation before testing, influences of different material properties, structure, and conformation must be further investigated.

Welding of the samples based on the same matrixes yielded welds that were stronger than the specimens themselves, resulting in breakages of the sample instead of the weld. Neat incompatible polymers (ABS and PP) were not possible to weld, due to lack of adhesion between the materials. Grafted ABS and grafted PPs adhered to each other even when combining incompatible polymer matrixes. With the study of thermomechanical properties of the ultrasonic welds via annealing at 160 °C and 180 °C we have recorded indications of significantly increasing weld strengths with vitrimer combinations than in combinations of grafted polymers, indicating that transesterification is positively influencing the weld strength.

Ultrasonic welding has proven to be the most versatile process since with induction we are limited to materials that respond to induction heating (magnetite filled composites), and with laser we are limited to a combination of laser transparent and absorbent material (CNT filled composites).

Overall, bonding strengths of overmoulded specimens of different materials, as well as welded were evaluated. Selfhealing behaviour of the materials was studied via scratch test as well. Considering the results and haptic observations of the processability yielded in the choice of PP-V4-EX, PP-V4-GB, and ABS-V3 based vitrimers and composites for use of CANs in hybrid technologies (Task 1.4).

Deviations from the GA

We presume that the present report covers all the aspects of Task 1.3, without deviations from GA.

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